

PROMISING TECHNOLOGIES TO REDUCE GLOBAL AND LOCAL AVIATION EMISSIONS

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Climate change is the megatrend that will have the biggest impact on the development of sustainable air transportation in near future. Aviation sector is expected to triple its proportional share (taking in mind only the development of usual air traffic without the contribution of the new Urban Air Mobility and other Advanced Air Mobility approaches) of a Paris compatible 1.5°C budget. ICAO basket of measures to keep the temperature change under this limit, including aircraft technology (up to 25%) and operation improvement (up to 9%) for fuel burn reduction by engines and new revolutionary designs of the aircraft, deployment of sustainable alternative fuels (over 40% of fuel burn reduction), market-based measures as pushing system for quicker and more efficient implementation of the first three, etc. Pioneering sustainable technology is allowing the civil aviation sector to embrace the next generation of aviation through electrification and alternative fuels including hydrogen. If to look at new supersonic aircraft future technologies are considered in mostly traditional development of emission reduction in combination with SAF for fuel burn by their engines (as considered now by EU SENECA project).

Radically new innovative aircraft concepts are necessary for implementation in aircraft design, which efficiency in emission reduction should be much higher than for current evolutionary concepts. The electrification of aircraft propulsion promises a significant reduction of aviation emissions and progress toward the strategic goals achievement. The first recommendation for EU EFACA project relates to the implementation of hybrid electric propulsion technology for propeller-driven regional aircraft. Principles of aircraft hybrid electrification should be enough for necessary emission reduction of GHGs by regional aircraft in flight, so as the goals in aircraft noise and local air quality should be reached.

Hydrogen fuel, which is burnt in combustion chambers of the engines directly (instead of usual fossil fuel or/and SAF from renewable resources), is the crucial potential technology for eliminating aircraft GHG emissions for the most popular groups of aircraft – short/medium range and long-range aircraft (their contribution in aviation sector is over the 90 %). Airbus is evaluating several hydrogen approaches for future aircraft designs (ZEROe), which include “direct hydrogen” and “hydrogen fuel cells”. With hydrogen as a fuel, either in combustion engines or used in a fuel cell, there are no in-flight CO₂ emissions whatsoever. The second recommendation for EU EFACA project relates to the implementation of hydrogen fuel cells and liquid hydrogen fuel system for propeller-driven regional aircraft and jet airliner correspondingly.

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